

IPBES Transformative Change Assessment Chapter 5. Data Management Report 5.1. Instruments, actions and strategies for transformative change

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The scoping report for chapter 5 of the present assessment states that this chapter will assess the instruments and practical strategies for concrete action to foster, accelerate and maintain transformative change toward visions, scenarios and pathways for a sustainable world. The purpose of this review is to create an inventory of instruments (e.g., policies) that have been proposed to realize transformative change, and to organize elements in the inventory in actions, which have been further classified in 5 strategies. The inventory includes instruments and actions that have been proposed but never tested or already implemented by different actor groups in different social sectors.

Process Overview

Protocol

The inventory started with a review of previous IPBES-related work. Expert knowledge supported by Artificial Intelligence (AI) was used to compile the required information.

Step 1:

Type of analysis/search/review: Identification of actions for transformative change for sustainability from previous and ongoing IPBES assessments.

Search languages: English.

Sample extracted: Three chapters of completed IPBES assessment reports and one report of an Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop; the documents considered were:

- Chapter 6: Options for Decision Makers of the IPBES Global assessment report
- Chapter 6: Policy options and capacity development to operationalize the inclusion of diverse values of nature in decision-making of the IPBES Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature.
- Chapter 6: Policy options for governing sustainable use of wild species of the IPBES Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species.
- Report of the second Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop for the IPBES assessment of transformative change: reviewing the first order draft.

Location and format of the data (A): 1_IPBES_TCA_DMR5.1_considered IPBES reports_(A).bib

Treatment applied: Instruments, options, and actions for sustainability were extracted from tables, figures, supplementary materials, and text. Duplicates were identified and removed from the final list. Additional instruments and options were included based on expert knowledge and queries to AI.

Sample extracted: 230 options from IPBES reports

Location and format of the data (B): 2_IPBES_TCA_DMR5.1_initial options list_(B).csv

Fields extracted:

- Name of instrument, option, or action for sustainability
- Description (the context the option has been suggested or can be operationalized in, the specific instruments and actions to operate the option)
- Actors involved
- Examples (if applicable)

Step 2:

Type of analysis/search/review: Using author's expert knowledge and through several iterations, instruments obtained from IPBES documents were categorized in a three-level structure where instruments are coded into action, organized in 5 strategies.

Sample extracted: 566 terms for instruments (organized in 5 strategies and 26 actions)

Location of the data:

- 566 terms for instruments:
https://rkrug.github.io/strategies_actors_tch/input/search%20terms/strategies_options.md
- 316 terms organized in actor groups and social sectors:
https://rkrug.github.io/strategies_actors_tch/input/search%20terms/actors.m

Treatment applied: A group of 4 assessment experts categorized all terms identified into the five overarching strategies identified in chapter 5, which were further subdivided into options. Each option included terms for different instruments and actions.

This first classification was then refined using two complementary approaches:

- First, the assessment experts reviewed the classification to increase coherence within categories and to add additional terms for instruments and actions based on their expert knowledge.
- Second, in May 2024, assessment experts also used AI (ChatGPT) to fill potential gaps in the list of instruments and actions. Specifically, for each option, ChatGPT was asked to "list instruments or actions used for [*name of action*]". Expert knowledge was used to manually review AI responses and terms for relevant instruments and actions were added to the final list.

For each instrument and action in the list, the assessment experts ran a search using the 566 key terms in the titles and abstracts of two corpora: the transformative change assessment corpus of literature (comprising approximately 4.7 million documents related to transformative change and nature – see related Data Management Report) and the cases corpus (a subset of 45,000 case studies from the assessment corpus). The number of hits per individual search term helped to identify the frequency of mention of specific instruments (ranging from 0 to several million). These results were used to improve the search terms by correcting typos and refining terms with a large number of hits. The percentages of occurrence of instruments per strategies in each corpus are presented in figure 5.3.

The assessment experts then ran a combined search for each action, which includes all terms for instruments in a given action. As the search protocol limited the search to 750 characters, searches for four actions with longer lists of instruments were subdivided. The results of these subdivided searches were aggregated afterwards, removing duplicates.

The final list of actors is organized in 17 actor groups and four social sectors.

End point: Chapter 5 is organized in 5 strategies, subdivided into a total of 22 actions.

See figure 5.3, sections 5.2; 5.3; 5.4; 5.5; 5.6 and 5.7.

Definition of files

ID	Names	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR5.1 _considered IPBES reports_(A)	Bib Tex	4 KG	Four IPBES documents considered
B	2_IPBES_TCA_DMR5.1 _initial options list _11_2024_(B)	csv	76 KB	Initial list of 230 options

